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MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGY DIRECTED ON DEVELOPMENT OF THE COMMUNICATION COMPETENCY IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the modern pedagogical technology directed on development of the communication competency in Modern English for students of Higher Educational Institutions.

Today not for nothing question is put about importance and study computer technology by modern teacher. The Internet is useful both are students and teachers. Use online education in scholastic process enables to study some subject simultaneously

with the other subject on professions, since integration promotes the improvement of the scholastic process углом. The Facilities computer technology allow to realize the interaction between teacher and training in dialogue. Such type of the interaction relieves the process of the exchange by information. The Combination of the traditional methods and facilities of the education with computer technology can become the reason of increasing to progresses, skill student and stimulus of the development of the independent work.

Choice educational technology for achievement integer and decisions of the problems, put delivered within the framework of scholastic discipline "Foreign language" is conditioned by need to form beside student complex competency, required for realization of the interpersonal interaction and cooperation in condition to communications, as well as provide the required quality of the education on all his (its) stage. The Forms and technologies, used for learning English, realize and larval approaches, which in turn, promote to shaping and development but to language personality, capable to realize the productive contact with carrier of the other cultures; of the abilities student to realize the different types to activity, using English; in abilities student; to their readiness to and as well as promote increasing of the creative potential to personalities to realization of their own professional duties.

The scholastic process is based on models of the mixed education, which helps effectively to combine the traditional forms of the education and new technologies. Specifics of discipline "Foreign language" defines need more broadly use new educational technologies, alongside with traditional methods, directed on shaping base skill to practical activity with use mainly frontal forms of the work.

When learning foreign language are used following educational technologies:

- Technology of the communication education - is directed on shaping communication student, which is base, required for adapting to modern condition to communications;
- Technology differentiated of the education - expects the realization to cognitive activity student with account their individual abilities, possibilities and interest,

encouraging their realize its creative potential. Creation and use diagnostic test are an integral part given to technologies;

- Technology of the module education - provides the fission of the contents of discipline on it is enough autonomous sections the modules, integrated in the general course;
 - Information-communication technologies - increase the frames of the educational process, raising his (its) practical directivity, promote the of the independent work and increasing to cognitive activity.
- 2 Types technology stand out within the framework of;
- Technology of the use the computer programs - allows effectively process of the education language on all level. The Multimedia programs are intended both for, and independent functioning student and

are directed on development grammatical classes and lexical skill;

- Internet-technologies - give the broad possibilities for information retrieval, development international scientific project, conduct of the scientific studies;
 - Technology to personal of the education - helps to realize larval-oriented approach, considering individual particularities and need students;
 - Technology of the testing - is used for checking level assimilations lexical, grammatical knowledge within the framework of module on determined stage of the education. The Realization of the checking with use of technologies of the testing to quality all international exam on foreign language. Besides, given technology allows the teacher to reveal and systematize the aspects, requiring additional work;
 - Design technology - is oriented on modeling of the social interaction student for the reason decisions of the task, which is defined within the framework of training student, selecting that or other application domain.
- Use to design technology promotes the realization nature competency, forum in process of the education English;
- Technology of the education in cooperation - realizes the idea of the mutual education, realizing as the individual, so and collective responsibility for decision of the scholastic tasks;
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- Playing technology - allows to develop the skills of consideration of the row of the possible ways of the decision of the problems, actuating thinking student and revealing larval potential each student;
 - Technology of the development of the critical thinking - promotes shaping to

many-sided personality, capable critically to pertain to information, skill to select information for decision of the put delivered task.

The Realization and larval of the approach with use enumerated technology provides active and interactive of the form of the education such as business and role of the play, analysis concrete situation, collective

activity, debates, functioning on project of the research nature and est. At occupations with use interactive forms form not less 70% all class occupation. Complex use in scholastic process all above named technology larval, knowledge-based activity, develop the cognitive processes, promote shaping a competency, which must possess the future specialist.

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